

An Analysis of Students Reading Comprehension in Comprehending Descriptive Text at the First Grade Students in SMKN 5 Padang

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Abstract: The purpose of this research was to describe students' skill of class X Teknik Instalasi Tenaga Listrik (TITL3) at SMK Negeri Padang in comprehending descriptive text in comprehending text there are 5 aspects can help the students to comprehend the text that is identifying main idea, find specific information, references, inference and vocabulary. The kind of this research was descriptive research. The population of this research were students of class X TITL 3 (Teknik Instalasi Tenaga Listrik) SMK Negeri 5 Padang. The total number of sample members were 20 students chosen by cluster random sampling. The data were collected by reading test the students answer the questions based on the text. The result of this research showed the students skill in comprehending descriptive text was moderate. It was proved that 55% students had moderate in determining topic. Students ability in identification was moderate, it was proved 45% students had moderate. Students ability in description was moderate, 70% students had moderate. Students ability in identifying supporting detail was moderate, in fact 40% students had moderate, and students ability in vocabulary was low, it was proved 55% students had moderate.

Keywords: Reading, Comprehending, Descriptive text.

1. Introduction

English considered as an important subject; Therefore, the government required every school starting from junior high school up to university to learn English. In English there are four skill that is reading, speaking, writing and listening. The problem reading skill faced by students is most of students difficult to understand about the text. In reading learning process the students must understand what the content of text to get the information from it.

The information cannot receive if they do not know about the content of the text. There are some texts teach at the first grade in senior high school that is descriptive text, narrative text, and recount text. In this research, the writer focusses on descriptive text.

Based on English syllabus of first grade in curriculum 2013, students are expected to be able to comprehend descriptive text. Descriptive text is a kind text to describe place, person, and things. The generic structure of descriptive text is identification and description. Based on the researcher's experience during teaching practice in SMKN 5 Padang, the researcher found

some problems dealing with students in reading comprehension in descriptive text. The first problem are the students did not understand how to determining topic of descriptive text.

Topic is something or object that will be discussed in reading, therefore to understand a text we must first determine what topics are discussed in the text. in the descriptive text there are several things that will be discussed, for example about people, things, places, and animal.

The second problem are students did not know about the generic structure of descriptive text, which is consist of identification and description. In identification the text introduces the thing or object that can be describe, while in the description the text describing or explain about the thing that has been introduce in the identification.

The third problem is students difficult to understand the supporting detail of the paragraph. Students difficult to understand the supporting detail causes the students confuse about the topic and what is the text about. The last problem is the students lack of vocabulary, makes the students difficult to understand meaning and the content of descriptive text.

This makes students did not interest in reading English text, because they only read the text but do not understand what they read. Based on the identification of the problem above, the researcher focused to analyze the students ability in comprehending descriptive text at the first grade students of SMKN 5 Padang to comprehending the topic, generic structure and vocabulary. Research Questions are:

- 1) How is students ability to determine topic of the descriptive text?
- 2) How is the students ability to identify the generic structure of the descriptive text?
- 3) How is students ability to identify the supporting detail of descriptive text?
- 4) How is the students vocabulary in reading the descriptive text? Purpose of Research:(1) To Analyze the students reading ability determining topic in descriptive text. (2) To Analyze the students reading ability in generic structure of descriptive text. (3) To Analyze the students reading ability in comprehending the supporting detail of descriptive text. (4) To

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Analyze students vocabulary in comprehending descriptive text.

2. Research Findings

Based on the purpose of this research, the researcher showed the findings of the research as follows:

- 1) *To Analyze the students reading ability in determining topic.* In determining topic, the result of the data analysis showed that the highest score of this component was 20 which were got by 6 students and the moderate score was 15 which was got by 11 students. Thus, there were 3 students which were got the lowest score 5, it can be seen that student's reading ability in comprehending the descriptive text in determining the topic of the descriptive text was moderate with the percentage 55% of Students can answer main idea clearly. 30% students got high score, it means only 30% of students really have good ability in determining topic. Although 15% students can't present main idea clearly.
- 2) *To Analyze the students reading ability in identification of generic structure.* In identification, the result of the data analysis showed that the highest score of this component was 15 which were got by 4 students and the moderate score was 10 which was got by 9 students. Thus, there were 7 students which were got the lowest score 5, another students got low ability. From the explanation above, it can be seen that student's reading ability in comprehending the descriptive text to show description had same percentage between moderate and low. the percentage showed 40% of the students did not understand how to identified the description in the descriptive text and 40% students had moderate ability in identifying description of descriptive text. Only 20% Student's answer the question correctly and had high reading ability in comprehending descriptive text.
- 3) *To Analyze the students reading ability in description of generic structure.* In description, the result of the data analysis showed that the highest score of this component was 20 got by 15% students, while 70% students got moderate ability in describing topic in descriptive text. Another students got low ability in description of the topic with percentage 15%.
- 4) *To Analyze the students reading ability in comprehending the supporting detail in descriptive text.* In comprehending the supporting detail in descriptive text, the result of the data analysis showed that the students had high ability in this component was 20% students got high ability. meanwhile 40% students had moderate ability in this component. 40% another students also had low ability in this component.
- 5) *To Analyze the students reading ability in vocabulary.* In vocabulary the result of the data analysis showed that the highest score of this component was 20 got by 20% students, it means 20% students good in

vocabulary. While 35% students had moderate ability in vocabulary. Another students got low ability in vocabulary.

3. Discussion

Based on the researcher findings, the researcher found that student's reading ability in comprehending the descriptive text from each element was different each other. There were 5 elements of reading comprehension: main idea, identification, description, supporting detail and vocabulary. It will be explained in detail below:

The first in determining topic, the students had moderate ability. It was because 55% students were in moderate ability, they can explain about the topic but not overall. Only 6 students understand how to determining topic. 15% of the students got the low score, it means 3 students did not know how to determining topic.

The second, in determining identification of generic structure, the student's had moderate ability. It was because 45% students were in moderate ability. Only 4 students understand how to identification the topic. 7 of the students got the low score, it means they did not know how to determining the main idea.

The third, in the description of the topic, the students also had moderate ability. it was because 70% students were in moderate ability. meanwhile 15% of another students had high score. They had the high ability to identified the identification in the descriptive text. Meanwhile 15% another students had low ability in identified the identification of descriptive text. Most of them did not understand the function of the identification of descriptive text. It was making students had moderate ability in the identification.

The fourth, in the comprehending supporting detail, the students had moderate ability only 40%. It means 8 students had moderate ability in identifying the description of the descriptive text. However, 40% students had low ability in identifying the description. Meanwhile there were 20% students in high ability. It means only 4 students can answer the question correctly and understand about description of the descriptive text.

The last, in the vocabulary, the students had low ability, it can see from there were 11 students got the low ability. It means 55% students had lack of vocabulary. Meanwhile there were 20% of students had high ability. 35% of students had moderate ability.

From the discussion of research ability in reading comprehension in comprehending the descriptive text was moderate. Therefore, the students should be improving their reading ability in comprehending the descriptive text.

4. Conclusion

Based on the finding of the research, the researcher concluded that: The student's reading ability in determining the topic in the descriptive text was moderate. It was because 55% students had moderate ability. It means 11 students can answer the topic clearly.

The student's reading ability in the generic structure the

descriptive text was moderate. It was because 45% had moderate ability. The student's reading ability in identifying the supporting detail was moderate with the percentage 40% students had moderate ability in identifying the supporting detail. They can answer the basic of the supporting detail.

The student's reading ability in the vocabulary was low. It was because 55% students had low ability in the vocabulary. Some students answer 3 from 5 question about vocabulary clearly.

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